

Role of Toxic Aromatic Compounds in Nitrogen Enrichment

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The formation of amino acids in systems not containing any source of nitrogen, utilising compounds having antiseptic properties such as phenol, resorcinol etc has been investigated and the results conclusively showed that nitrogen enrichment is a photochemical process and not purely a bacterial process. The energy required for this process is obtained by the oxidation of the carbonaceous compounds and by the photolytic fission of water.

GRÜTTONEON¹ observed nitrogen fixation by utilising toxic compounds such as phenols and salicylates. Dhar² and co-workers observed fixation of atmospheric nitrogen in the slow oxidation of various organic compounds such as glycerol, acetophenone etc by air, mixed with chemically pure surfaces such as Al₂O₃, TiO₂, Fe₂O₃ and ZnO etc. Hannequine³ *et al* have reported the general occurrence of *para*-hydroxybenzoic acid, vanillic acid and *para*-coumaric acids in certain soils. Dhar pointed out that the chemical energy liberated from the oxidation of carbohydrates, fats, etc, can enrich the system from nitrogen point of view, even in dark and in the absence of bacteria.

In the present work, we have carried out systematic investigations of nitrogen fixation using aromatic toxic organic compounds such as phenol, resorcinol which can destroy bacteria. Russel and Buddin⁴ found that the antiseptic compounds such as phenols and cresols, when used in their experiments of nitrogen fixation destroyed the microorganisms. Light plays an important role in many chemical reactions and hence the influence of light on carbon-nitrogen transformations has also been studied.

Experimental

200 g of sieved and oven dried titania were taken in 500 ml conical flasks. To this, required quantities of phenol or resorcinol and phosphates were introduced as 1% carbon and 0.5% P₂O₅ as CaHPO₄·2H₂O, respectively. The contents of each flask were thoroughly mixed and the mixture made uniform. Two identical sets were arranged side by side, one of which was exposed to sun light and the other was covered with a thick black cloth. In all the experimental flasks the moisture content was maintained at 40% level throughout the experiment. All these flasks were plugged with cotton wool.

For the sterile sets, the entire above process was repeated and then all flasks sterilised for 20-30 min at 15 lbs pressure and at 115°, before exposing to light.

After definite intervals of time the contents of one flask from each set (sterile, unsterile, exposed and covered) was well ground and transferred into a 250 ml volumetric flask and the volume made up with water. An aliquot was taken and evaporated on a waterbath with a drop of conc. H₂SO₄ to prevent the escape of ammonia, and analysed for total nitrogen and total carbon according to the methods of Robinson, Mclean and Williams⁵ and of Treadwell and Hall⁶, respectively. For other estimations the standard methods were used.

Discussion

From the experimental record it is interesting to note that nitrogen has been observed in the systems containing phenol and resorcinol which are well known germicidals and thus the possibilities of bacterial fixation of nitrogen can easily be ruled out. These results bring out the marked significance of surface and light in oxidation reactions as the oxidation of carbon in the sets exposed to light in both sterile and unsterile conditions is a combination of photochemical, surface and catalytic reactions while the oxidation of carbon in the covered sets under sterile conditions, where microbial and light actions are ruled out, is purely a surface and catalytic process. Thus it is clear from these results that surface and catalytic reactions accelerated by light absorption play an important role in the transformation and oxidation of organic compounds and fixation of atmospheric nitrogen. Dhar postulated that the important photochemical reaction involved in plant photosynthesis was the decomposition of water by the absorption of light. In explaining the process of nitrogen fixation, the best mechanism seems to be the same, i.e., decomposition of water into H and OH by the absorption of energy obtained from the oxidation of energy rich materials like glucose, cellulose, lignin, fat etc as follows :

SEN : ROLE OF TOXIC AROMATIC COMPOUNDS IN NITROGEN ENRICHMENT

TABLE 1—200 g TITANIA + 40% MOISTURE (CONTROL),

AVERAGE TEMPERATURE = 34°
UNSTERILE SETS

Period of exposure in days	Total Carbon (g)	Total Nitrogen (g)	Efficiency	NH ₃ - N (g)	NO ₃ - N (g)	Amino acids identified chromatographically	Amount of amino acids with respect to glycine (g)	Available P ₂ O ₅ (g)
0						LIGHT		
60	0.0426	0.0082	—	—	0.0016	—	—	0.0086
120	0.0276	0.0085	20.0	0.0002	—	—	—	0.0091
240	0.0228	0.0086	20.4	0.0003	—	—	—	0.0098
	0.0173	0.0087	19.4	0.0003	0.0017	Gly, Al, Glu, Va	0.0265	0.0101
0						DARK		
60	0.0426	0.0082	—	—	0.0016	—	—	0.0086
120	0.0320	0.0083	10.2	—	—	—	—	0.0088
240	0.0250	0.0084	11.2	—	—	—	—	0.0090
	0.0196	0.0085	9.8	0.0002	—	—	—	0.0092

TABLE 2—200 g OF TITANIA + 1% C AS PHENOL + 40% MOISTURE

0						LIGHT		
60	2.0426	0.0082	—	—	0.0016	—	—	0.0086
120	1.6531	0.0213	33.8	0.0026	0.0050	Gly, Al, Va, Glu	0.4349	0.0098
240	1.3775	0.0309	34.2	0.0032	0.0062	Gly, Al, Va, Glu, Asp	0.7862	0.0104
	1.0186	0.0414	32.5	0.0035	0.0067	Gly, Al, Va, Glu, Asp, Threo	0.9275	0.0110
0						DARK		
60	2.0426	0.0082	—	—	0.0016	—	—	0.0086
120	1.7979	0.0119	15.2	0.0011	0.0020	Gly, Al	0.945	0.0095
240	1.6764	0.0154	15.6	0.0015	0.0028	Gly, Al, Glu, Asp	0.1273	0.0098
	1.3111	0.0183	13.8	0.0017	0.0030	Glu, Gly, Al, Va, Asp, Threo	0.1489	0.0100

TABLE 3—200 g TITANIA + 1% C AS RESORCINOL + 40% MOISTURE

0						LIGHT		
60	2.0426	0.0082	—	—	0.0016	—	—	0.0086
120	1.6303	0.0234	37.0	0.0031	0.0060	Gly, Al, Va, Glu	0.7866	0.0112
240	1.3140	0.0355	37.6	0.0036	0.0069	Gly, Al, Va, Glu, Asp	1.5169	0.0118
	0.9140	0.0492	36.4	0.0039	0.0076	Gly, Al, Va, Glu, Asp, Threo	1.5632	0.0123
0						DARK		
60	2.0426	0.0082	—	—	0.0016	—	—	0.0086
120	1.7751	0.0130	18.0	0.0014	0.0028	Gly, Al	0.1037	0.0098
240	1.5597	0.0169	18.5	0.0019	0.0036	Gly, Al, Glu, Asp	0.1549	0.0102
	1.2759	0.0208	16.5	0.0022	0.0040	Gly, Al, Glu, Asp, Va, Threo	0.1567	0.0105

TABLE 4—200 g TITANIA + 1% C AS PHENOL + 0.5% P₂O₅ AS CaHPO₄·2H₂O

0						LIGHT		
60	2.0426	0.0082	—	—	0.0016	—	—	0.4572
120	1.4556	0.0377	50.4	0.0051	0.0084	Gly, Al, Va, Glu, Se	0.6836	0.4683
240	1.1618	0.0535	51.2	0.0058	0.0098	Gly, Al, Va, Glu, Se, Asp	0.9887	0.4786
	0.7422	0.0721	49.2	0.0063	0.0104	Gly, Al, Va, Glu, Se, Asp, Threo	1.2651	0.4804
0						DARK		
60	2.0426	0.0082	—	—	0.0016	—	—	0.4572
120	1.6813	0.0176	26.2	0.0027	0.0048	Gly, Al	0.1850	0.4587
240	1.4751	0.0234	26.8	0.0035	0.0054	Gly, Al, Glu, Asp	0.2965	0.4639
	1.0802	0.0322	25.0	0.0039	0.0059	Gly, Al, Glu, Asp, Threo, Se	0.3073	0.4679

TABLE 5—200 g TITANIA + 1% C AS RESORCINOL + 0.5% P₂O₅ AS CaHPO₄·2H₂O

0						LIGHT		
60	2.0426	0.0082	—	—	0.0016	—	—	0.4572
120	1.4361	0.0407	53.6	0.0056	0.0093	Gly, Al, Va, Glu, Se	1.0236	0.4692
240	1.1421	0.0572	54.4	0.0063	0.0105	Gly, Al, Va, Glu, Se, Asp	1.9562	0.4814
	0.7237	0.0767	82.0	0.0068	0.0110	Gly, Al, Va, Glu, Se, Asp, Threo	2.0313	0.4871
0						DARK		
60	2.0426	0.0082	—	—	0.0016	—	—	0.4572
120	1.6705	0.0184	27.4	0.0030	0.0052	Gly, Al	0.2006	0.4594
240	1.4615	0.0244	28.0	0.0037	0.0059	Gly, Al, Glu, Asp	0.3117	0.4648
	1.0709	0.0344	27.0	0.0042	0.0064	Gly, Al, Glu, Asp, Va, Threo, Se	0.3200	0.4690

TABLE 6—200 g TITANIA +1% C AS PHENOL +40% MOISTURE						STERILE SETS	AVERAGE TEMPERATURE = 34°	
Period of exposure in days	Total Carbon (g)	Total Nitrogen (g)	Efficiency	NH ₃ -N (g)	NO ₂ -N (g)	Amino acids identified chromatographically	Amount of aminoacids with respect to glycine (g)	Available P ₂ O ₅ (g)
LIGHT								
0	2.0426	0.0082	—	—	0.0016	—	—	0.0086
60	1.6777	0.0193	30.6	0.0019	0.0037	Gly, Al, Va, Glu	0.3456	0.0094
120	1.4213	0.0275	31.2	0.0025	0.0046	Gly, Al, Va, Glu, Asp	0.5374	0.0099
240	1.1338	0.0353	29.8	0.0028	0.0052	Gly, Al, Va, Glu, Asp, Threo	0.7361	0.0105
DARK								
0	2.0426	0.0082	—	—	0.0016	—	—	0.0086
60	1.8241	0.0111	13.4	0.0007	0.0018	—	—	0.0090
120	1.6273	0.0139	13.8	0.0011	0.0022	—	—	0.0094
240	1.3792	0.0160	11.8	0.0013	0.0025	Gly, Al, Glu, Asp, Va	0.632	0.0297

TABLE 7—200 g TITANIA +1% C AS RESORCINOL +40% MOISTURE								
LIGHT								
0	2.0426	0.0082	—	—	0.0016	—	—	0.0086
60	1.6573	0.0211	33.6	0.0023	0.0041	Gly, Al, Va, Glu	0.4693	0.0098
120	1.3928	0.0304	34.2	0.0029	0.0054	Gly, Al, Va, Glu, Asp	0.8732	0.0103
240	1.0952	0.0392	32.8	0.0033	0.0062	Gly, Al, Va, Glu, Asp, Threo	0.9621	0.0109
DARK								
0	2.0426	0.0082	—	—	0.0016	—	—	0.0086
60	1.7995	0.0118	14.8	0.0011	0.0022	—	—	0.0092
120	1.5961	0.0150	15.4	0.0016	0.0030	—	—	0.0096
240	1.3354	0.0173	13.0	0.0019	0.0035	Gly, Al, Glu, Asp, Va	0.0893	0.0099

TABLE 8—200 g TITANIA +1% C AS PHENOL +0.5% CaHPO ₄ .2H ₂ O +40% MOISTURE								
LIGHT								
0	2.0426	0.0082	—	—	0.0016	—	—	0.4572
60	1.4961	0.0339	46.6	0.0032	0.0060	Gly, Al, Va, Glu, Se	0.5061	0.4603
120	1.2246	0.0468	47.2	0.0040	0.0072	Gly, Al, Va, Glu, Se, Asp	0.8376	0.4649
240	0.8241	0.0630	45.0	0.0045	0.0055	Gly, Al, Va, Glu, Se, Asp, Threo	0.9653	0.4690
DARK								
0	0.0426	0.0082	—	—	0.0016	—	—	0.4572
60	1.7144	0.0156	22.8	0.0020	0.0038	—	—	0.4579
120	1.5129	0.0196	23.4	0.0026	0.0050	Gly, Al, Glu	0.1004	0.4548
240	1.1251	0.0274	21.0	0.0030	0.0058	Gly, Al, Glu, Asp, Va, Threo	0.1732	0.4589

TABLE 9—200 g TITANIA +1% C AS RESORCINOL +0.5% P ₂ O ₅ AS CaHPO ₄ .2H ₂ O +40% MOISTURE								
LIGHT								
0	2.0426	0.0082	—	—	0.0016	—	—	0.4572
60	1.4774	0.0355	48.4	0.0037	0.0064	Gly, Al, Va, Glu, Se	0.7937	0.4634
120	1.1955	0.0497	49.0	0.0045	0.0076	Gly, Al, Va, Glu, Asp, Se	1.1463	0.4692
240	0.7845	0.0667	46.5	0.0050	0.0086	Gly, Al, Va, Glu, Asp, Threo	1.1704	0.4737
DARK								
0	2.0426	0.0082	—	—	0.0016	—	—	0.4572
60	1.7047	0.0164	24.4	0.0023	0.0042	—	—	0.4583
120	1.4995	0.0217	25.0	0.0029	0.0050	Gly, Al, Glu	0.1337	0.4591
240	1.1001	0.0293	22.4	0.0035	0.0063	Gly, Al, Glu, Asp, Va, Threo	0.1982	0.4598

Gly = Glycine, Al = Alanine, Glu = Glutamic acid, Va = Valine, Asp = Aspartic acid, Threo = Threonine, Se = Serine

and this reaction is followed by the chemical combination of atomic hydrogen with atmospheric nitrogen leading to the formation of ammonia :

In the presence of sunlight, energy from the sun is absorbed by the system and is utilised in increasing the nitrogen fixation. The experiments of Bohr⁷, Einstein⁸ and Saha⁹ have shown that nitrogen molecules become active and partially ionised due to the ultraviolet radiations of wavelength between 2900 Å to 3200 Å. This active nitrogen facilitates its reaction with atomic hydrogen forming ammonia.

The ammonia formed readily undergoes oxidation and forms nitrite and nitrate which finally forms amino acids and protein.

There is no doubt that both essential and non-essential amino acids are created in the system in the process of atmospheric nitrogen fixation caused by the energy liberated in the slow oxidation of organic compounds like phenol and resorcinol. It seems that the amino acids obtained with phenol

and resorcinol are almost the same and they appear to be derived from the process of fixation of atmospheric nitrogen on titania surface.

The phosphated and exposed sets are richer in amino acids than the unphosphated and covered sets. No amino acid could be detected in the covered sets under sterile condition during the first 120 days. In the covered and phosphated sets under sterile condition a few amino acids could be detected after 60 days.

These observations clearly show the marked influence of light on nitrogen fixation and subsequent utilisation of the fixed nitrogen in the formation of amino acids. It is also clear from these observations that when dicalcium phosphate was added to the system, not only did the efficiency of nitrogen fixation increase but the rate of fall of efficiency of nitrogen fixation was checked and the amount of nitrogen fixed both under sterile and unsterile conditions also increased.

During the process of ammonification and subsequent nitrification of amino acids and proteins, the highly explosive and unstable substance ammonium nitrite is formed as an intermediate which readily breaks up

liberating energy, nitrogen gas and water, which causes the fall in efficiency with the lapse of time.

But in the presence of dicalcium phosphate containing Ca^{2+} ions, the more stable compound, calcium nitrite is produced instead of ammonium nitrite. Moreover, in the presence of phosphates more or less stable phosphoproteins are formed and they seem to resist the ammonification and nitrification processes and check nitrogen loss and thus increase the nitrogen status of the system.

When the energy materials undergo slow oxidation some organic acids may be produced in the system. It is well known that the decomposition of ammonium nitrite (NH_4NO_2) is accelerated in presence of acids. But in presence of dicalcium phosphate which acts as a buffer the increase of the H^+ ion concentration of the system is not appreciable. Hence the efficiency of nitrogen fixation is greater in presence of dicalcium phosphate than in its absence.

It appears therefore that for nitrogen fixation neither soil nor bacteria are absolutely essential; what really seems indispensable is a suitable solid surface where water, oxygen, nitrogen and an energy material are properly absorbed and are in intimate contact, so that the slow oxidation of the energy material leading to liberation of energy and subsequent nitrogen fixation can be possible.

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